

Implant Abutments Enhancing the Foundation of Dental Implants : A Review

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Abstract

Implant abutments are a fundamental component in dental implant restorations, serving as the interface between the implant fixture and the prosthesis. The growing variety of abutment designs, materials, and connection mechanisms presents challenges in clinical decision-making. This review provides an overview of implant abutment types, their biomechanical and aesthetic considerations, and their impact on long-term treatment success. By examining factors such as abutment fit, connection stability, and tissue response, clinicians can make informed choices that optimize implant function and aesthetics. A thorough understanding of abutment selection is critical for ensuring the longevity and success of single or multiple-unit implant restorations, ultimately improving patient outcomes and satisfaction.

Keywords : Implant dentistry, abutment connection, prosthetic interface, tissue integration, implant stability.

Introduction

The use of dental implants to replace natural teeth has become a standard procedure in modern restorative and surgical dentistry^[1]. In contemporary practice, dental implants play a crucial role in replacing missing teeth, offering superior support for both fixed and removable prostheses. Compared to traditional complete and partial dentures, implants enhance functionality and restore aesthetics more effectively^[2]. Prosthodontic rehabilitation using osseointegrated implants has emerged as the preferred treatment option for partially or completely edentulous patients^[3]. The success of implants is a key factor that significantly impacts clinical practice and encourages patients to opt for implant-supported prostheses^[4].

Implant-supported restorations have become a widely preferred treatment option for rehabilitating partially edentulous patients. The increasing adoption of dental implants has led clinicians to explore various implant materials and treatment protocols, further broadening their application. This advancement has contributed to the development of “restoration-driven” implant dentistry^[5]. In this regard, a thorough understanding of implant abutments and their design principles plays a crucial role in successful implantation.

An abutment is a component of the implant system that connects to a prepared tooth and is designed to be screwed into the implant body. It serves as the key element providing retention for the prosthesis. The abutment consists of three main parts: the base, which fits into the internal structure of the implant; the head, which extends outward and functions as a prosthetic retainer; and the collar, which sits at the gingival level, linking the base and head. Abutments can be categorized into one-piece or two-piece types, depending on their design^[6].

Classification of Implant Abutments

Several types of implant abutments have been documented in the literature for use in anterior implant-supported restorations. These abutments can be categorized based on various factors, including their connection method to the restoration, the material used for fabrication, the manufacturing process, the type of connection to the implant, and their color^[7].

Implant abutments can be classified based on several key factors, including their connection method to the restoration, type of

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implant connection, material composition, fabrication method, and color.

1. Method of Connection to Restoration:
 - Screw-retained abutment-crown complex
 - Two-piece design with a screw-retained crown over the abutment
 - Two-piece design with a cemented crown over the abutment
2. Abutment Connection to Implant:
 - External connection
 - Internal connection
3. Material Composition:
 - Titanium (including cast metal options such as noble, high noble, or base-metal alloy)
 - Cast metal with porcelain fused at the base
 - Alumina
 - Full zirconia
 - Zirconia with a titanium base (zirconia-titanium hybrid abutment)
4. Fabrication Method:
 - Prefabricated (unaltered or modified)
 - Custom cast abutment
 - Custom copy milled abutment
 - Custom CAD-CAM abutment
5. Color Variations:
 - Gold
 - Silver (metallic finish)
 - Pure white
 - Custom white
 - Custom pink/gingival shade at the cervical region

Additionally, implant abutments come in various designs, including standard abutments, estheticone abutments, angulated abutments, ceraone abutments, and overdenture abutments.

Types of Abutments

Standard Abutments

Standard abutments have a cylindrical design and come in various heights, accompanied by corresponding titanium abutment screws. Their base features a hexagonal shape that securely fits into the implant fixture. These abutments are commonly used in the fabrication of fixed bone-anchored bridges for edentulous patients. To facilitate oral hygiene, the junction between the abutment and the restoration is positioned 2mm above the oral mucosa^[8].

There are two primary impression techniques used with standard abutments:

- A. Pick-up (Open Tray) Impression Technique
- B. Transfer (Closed Tray) Impression Technique^[9]

One technique utilizes a tapered impression coping, which is screwed into the internal screw channel of the abutment. The impression is taken without removing the coping. Afterward, the coping is detached, connected to an analog, placed into the impression, and then used to pour the cast.

The other technique involves a square impression coping with undercuts that lock into the impression material. After taking the impression, the guide pins are unscrewed and removed. This method is considered more accurate. The base of the impression coping is round, and an anti-rotation feature is not required for multiple implant restorations.

For the final restoration, a gold alloy cylinder is placed over the standard abutment and incorporated into the final prosthesis after casting. Gold screws secure the gold cylinder to the abutment, ensuring stability. The final restoration is fixed in place using these gold screws, which are tightened to 10 N.cm^[10].

Angulated Abutments

Angulated abutments are designed with either a 30-degree or 17-degree angulation to address challenges related to implant positioning. Their base features a twelve-sided configuration, allowing for precise alignment. These abutments are primarily used in multiple implant restorations to correct implant angulation issues^[11].

Estheticone Abutments

Estheticone abutments are crafted from pure titanium and feature a hexagonal base with a tapered design. They are available in three sizes-corresponding to collar heights of one, two, and three millimeters. These abutments are specifically designed for aesthetic restorations, multiple implant-supported screw-retained prostheses, as well as ceramic-metal and cast-metal restorations^[12].

The restorations are positioned 2-3 mm subgingivally to create a natural appearance. The technique used for esthetic abutments is similar to that employed for standard abutments.

Ceraone Abutments

Ceraone abutments are made of pure titanium and are designed for cement-retained, single-tooth restorations. They come in various collar heights, ranging from 1 mm to 5 mm, and feature a hexagonal base. The abutment is secured to the implant using a gold alloy screw, tightened with a force of 32 Ncm.

Plastic impression copings attach to the abutment through frictional resistance and are removed along with the impression. Once the impression is taken, an analog is placed, and the cast is poured. Healing caps are used to preserve soft tissue support.

For all ceramic single-tooth restorations, porcelain is applied to ceramic caps. The final prosthesis can be cemented temporarily or permanently, with careful removal of excess cement being crucial to prevent complications^[13].

Overdenture Abutments

Abutments used for overdenture ball attachments are similar to standard abutments. The male component consists of a ball head on the abutment screw, while the female component is a plastic cap within the denture base. This plastic cap incorporates rubber O-rings that fit over the abutment screw, providing retention for the denture^[14].

Laboratory analogs are available, allowing for the option to incorporate the attachments either clinically or in the laboratory. This approach is both simple and time-saving.

Abutment Types for Anterior and Posterior Implants

Standard Abutments

Standard abutments are pre-made and typically made of titanium. They consist of two parts: the abutment itself and the abutment screw. These abutments come in various heights and feature smooth collars extending from the implant head to the crown margin. For example, the Nobel BiocareCeraone implant has a flat top and a raised hexagon that provides an anti-rotation mechanism for the abutment. The abutment is secured to the implant using a gold screw.

Some implants, like Astratech, Frialit, and Straumann, use a conical-headed abutment with a matched conical fit surface, along with an anti-rotational element. In single-tooth restorations, the coronal part of the abutment must provide adequate retention and resistance to secure the crown to the abutment using cement. Other designs, such as the Astratech single-tooth abutment, allow space between the abutment and the crown to facilitate cement release^[15].

Although the margins of these abutments do not always follow the gingival contour and may not be suitable for labially placed cases, they are easy to use, require minimal chairside time, and offer reliable retention and crown fit.

Prep-able Abutments

Prepable abutments feature a retentive element made from a block of metal, which is customized to fit an ideal preparation. The abutment is shaped extraorally using a high-speed drill. The gingival margin follows the natural gingival contour, positioned subgingivally on the labial side and supragingivally on the proximal and palatal sides. The metal surface that contacts the crown is left coarse to enhance retention, while the surface that contacts the tissue is smoothed^[16].

There are two methods for preparing prep-able abutments:

- 1. Single-Stage Preparation :** The abutment and final crown are produced in one stage, typically when the soft tissue is healthy. This method provides a good marginal fit, but there is a risk of poor long-term retention.
- 2. Two-Stage Preparation :** The abutment and provisional crown are prepared in the first stage. An impression is taken with the abutment in place, and the final crown is made in the second stage. This method offers more predictable results, especially when the soft tissue profile or emergence needs modification.

The two-stage approach is versatile, accommodating angulation changes, soft tissue remodeling, and providing a good emergence profile. However, it requires a more complex laboratory process, a second intraoral impression, and can result in a less predictable fit between the abutment and the final crown.

Fully Customized Abutments

Fully customized abutments are particularly beneficial in cases where the implant positioning is compromised. To create these abutments, an impression of the implant head is taken, and the abutment is positioned on the model. The shape of the abutment is then waxed onto the pattern before being cast in precious metal. This technique allows for adjustments to the long axis of the final restoration, providing more flexibility in aligning the

restoration correctly^[17].

CAD/CAM Abutments

CAD/CAM abutments are created using specialized software that allows for the design and visualization of the ideal abutment shape in 3D. First, an impression of the implant head is taken, and the working model is placed in a scanner. The software captures the implant position and angulation. The gingival margin position can be superimposed onto the digital image, which is then sent to a center where the abutment is fabricated in titanium. This method offers precise customization and enhances the accuracy of the final abutment design^[18].

Ceramic Abutments

Ceramic abutments are made from dense porcelain and are known for their high aesthetic quality, offering success rates. The final crown is typically fabricated from all-ceramic material and cemented using a tooth-colored luting agent. However, ceramic abutments are not ideal for situations that require significant changes in angulation^[19].

Abutments for Screw-Retained Crown

Abutments designed for bridges, such as the Estheticone by Nobel Biocare and Octa by Straumann, are used for screw-retained crowns. These abutments require a gold cylinder with an internal facet that engages the abutment to ensure secure attachment^[20].

Abutments for Cement-Retained Crown

One-piece abutments do not feature anti-rotational mechanisms and are typically used for multiple splinted implants. Their advantages include eliminating the need for a torque wrench, offering greater strength, preventing screw loosening, being more cost-effective, and allowing for easier seating. However, they are limited to multiple abutments and cannot be used with angled abutments.

Two-piece abutments, which engage anti-rotational features on the implant body, are secured using an abutment screw. These are used for single-tooth implants, indirect prosthesis fabrication, and angled abutment situations. While they offer anti-rotational resistance under shear forces, screw loosening can still occur, and they require torque and counter-torque devices for proper fixation^[21].

Abutment Designs

Abutments can be classified into three main categories: threaded (straight, prefabricated angled, custom), frictional (press fit, cold-welded), and non-threaded (cementable).

I. Threaded Abutments

- a. Straight :** These abutments are used when the axial inclination and parallelism of the implants are favorable. Some straight abutments include collars (e.g., Integral), while others, like those from Nobelpharma and IMZ, require separate trans-epithelial collars. Abutments such as Calcitek, Hexlock, and Sterioss feature an anti-rotation design.
- b. Pre-fabricated Angled :** Not all manufacturers offer pre-fabricated angled abutments, but some implant systems, including Integral, Sterioss, and Sustain, supply them.

Implant Innovations offers 15-30 degree angled, one-piece collared abutments. Steri-Oss provides a two-piece system featuring a hexagonal vertical component and a 15-25 degree angled post.

- c. Custom Abutments (Angled & Straight) :** Custom abutments are created by taking impressions or by using direct resin patterns. The internal threading of the implants is captured using a special transfer post, after which the impressions are removed, and the analog is attached before pouring the cast. Angulations greater than 25 degrees may result in excessive force on the implant^[22].

II. Frictional / Press-Fit Abutments

- Frictional or press-fit abutments are supplied by brands such as Stryker and Miter Blades. These abutments come in both straight and angled variants, with angles typically around 15 degrees. To insert these abutments, the head must be oriented correctly and then tapped firmly into place with a mallet. Once tapped in, the abutment cannot be removed, making it a secure and permanent attachment^[23].

III. Non-Threaded, Cementable Abutments

- The Core-Vent design system utilizes non-threaded, cementable abutments. In this system, abutment selection is typically made after the second stage of surgery.

Attachment of Abutment to Implants

- Modern systems primarily use retaining screws to attach abutments to implants. For implants with flat surfaces, one-piece attachments are typically used, but these are limited to multiple splinted implants and lack anti-rotation features. In contrast, abutments designed with anti-rotation features prevent unwanted movement. Current attachment systems include external hex, internal hex, spline, and morse-taper designs^[24].

Abutment Selection

- For optimal results, the labial margin should extend at least 1 mm subgingivally; however, if it extends more than 3 mm, seating the abutment and removing excess cement becomes challenging. In such cases, a preable abutment may be used to address any discrepancies. A vertical space of 3 mm typically ensures a favorable emergence profile. When the additional flare is needed within a limited vertical space, a wide-diameter preable abutment is appropriate. For slight labial angulation, a standard abutment is suitable, and similarly, standard abutments work well in interocclusal spaces of 6–7 mm, while a preable abutment is preferable when space is limited.
- Screw-retained abutments are easier to retrieve compared to cementable ones, which can be more challenging to remove. Additionally, in cases with heightened aesthetic requirements, porcelain abutments may be chosen. Final restorations on either metal or porcelain abutments must be fabricated with sufficient thickness to prevent any display of metal.

Conclusion

Dental implants have become the foremost treatment option for restoring patients with partial or complete tooth loss. The connection between the implant and abutment is crucial, as it ensures both lateral and rotational stability, which ultimately supports the overall stability of the implant-supported prosthesis.

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